

ACTIVE WING SHAPE RECONFIGURATION USING A VARIABLE CAMBER COMPLIANT WING SYSTEM

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ABSTRACT

A Variable Camber Compliant Wing was designed and fabricated at the US Air Force Research Laboratory based on compliant mechanisms and advanced manufacturing technologies, enabling a solution that is light weight, requires low power, and is low cost. The Air Force Research Laboratory demonstrates a new capability and technology for an active wing camber change without discrete control surfaces under realistic aerodynamic conditions. In this particular study, the wing was designed to adjust the wing camber by six percent chord while holding maximum camber location, and maximum thickness constant (emulating a continuous change between a NACA 2410 to NACA 8410 profile), but the design is not only limited to these airfoils. The design is unique; the entire skin is seamless and continuous, constructed from a single piece of non-stretchable composite skin. The smooth elastic deformation of the Variable Camber Compliant Wing is obtained through the underlying compliant mechanism. 2D camber change is achieved by single linear actuation to control both leading and trailing edge deflection. 3D shape change is also capable through camber variation along the span using a distributed compliance and actuation system. Proving the capability of a smooth 2D and 3D shape change would allow aircraft to significantly reduce fuel burn by continuously optimizing the wing L/D throughout the mission, as well as reduce airframe noise caused by holes and gaps existing on a conventional wing. The wing was tested in the U.S. Air Force Vertical Wind Tunnel Facility in order to understand the inherently flexible adaptive wing structure and its aeroelastic effect under aerodynamic forces using state of the art measurement and visualization techniques.

1 INTRODUCTION

The United States Air Force consumes over two billion gallons of fuel per year and creates an operational energy expense of approximately ten billion dollars per year. As of 2011, jet fuel comprises 86% of the Air Force energy budget and over 8% of the total Air Force budget [1]. National, DoD, and AF policy, guidance, and plans have been developed towards the goal of making AF aircraft more energy efficient and reducing the AF's energy bill. Range is an excellent proxy for aircraft energy efficiency and it directly relates to ISR asset availability. The Breguet range equation (1) gives the parameters which govern overall aircraft efficiency; propulsion efficiency (specific fuel consumption - SFC), aerodynamic efficiency (lift-to-drag ratio - L/D), weight of the payload (W_{PL}), and structural efficiency (airframe empty weight - W_O).

$$Range = \frac{V}{SFC} * \frac{L}{D} \ln\left(1 + \frac{W_{fuel}}{W_{PL} + W_O}\right) \quad (1)$$

Current wings suffer from low aerodynamic efficiency due to sharp corners and gaps created by discrete control surfaces. Elimination of discontinuous surfaces can provide lower drag and increase vehicle endurance. The Air Force Research Laboratory (AFRL) has developed a novel adaptive Variable Camber Compliant Wing (VCCW) that can actively re-contour the airfoil camber using

compliant mechanisms (Figure 1). A VCCW with distributed camber control would be able to reconfigure itself through the continuous deformation of the structure to optimize its geometry to suite the current altitude, airspeed, and lift-to-drag (L/D) ratio requirements. VCCW can also avoid undesirable aerodynamic conditions such as separated flow and increased parasitic drag through the seamless skin construction without holes and gaps. This can increase overall range (Eq. 1) and endurance of an aircraft in addition to control surface effectiveness and power reductions.

In addition to the potential for the VCCW to adapt to current flight conditions for efficiency gains, the VCCW would enable wing reconfiguration to decrease noise. Flap side edge noise can be a large contribution to overall airframe noise [2]. The VCCW with seamless skin would significantly reduce or eliminate flap side edge noise by eliminating control surface gaps and edges. Airfoil trailing edge noise scales with V^5 [3], and in general, flying slower can reduce airfoil self-noise. A previous study investigating the relationship between airfoil self-noise and airfoil camber has found that increasing camber, and thus lift, can decrease noise by allowing decreased airspeed, and decreased angle of attack [4]. A VCCW would allow reconfiguration of wing section shape during various mission/flight segments to decrease noise.

The VCCW discussed in this paper was designed and built to demonstrate a seamless skin VCCW concept on the benchtop and in the wind tunnel at low flight speeds and moderate Reynolds number similar to the environment of a small unmanned aerial system.

Figure 1: The VCCW design concept enables profile camber change with a continuous outer mold line. The section view shows three different section profile configurations with different values of maximum camber.

2 CONFORMAL WING TECHNOLOGY

The notion of a morphing wing is not a new concept, as it was pioneered by the Wright Brothers during the first moments of three-axis controlled flight. Originally, the Wright Brothers used wing warping to allow a pilot to steer an aircraft to maintain its equilibrium [5]. In the early 1900s, wing warping made it difficult to control the aircraft and was much more liable to cause structural failure. However, more advanced optimization tools as well as materials are available to revisit this concept once again. Several programs are now trying to incorporate this technology to optimize flight performance qualities.

The Mission Adaptive Wing reconsidered this technology by incorporating separate leading and trailing edge mechanisms made up of rigid mechanical linkages. This allowed variable camber, roll control, and gust load alleviation to optimize cruise and manoeuvre conditions [6]. Although this structure provided a continuous contour to reduce drag, the structure was extremely complex, increasing the weight (Figure 2). The Defence Advanced Research Projects Agency (DARPA) Smart Wing Project also used a smoothly contoured trailing edge that demonstrated variable wing twist. Smart Material allowed a trailing edge maximum deflection of ± 25 degrees. The associated difficulties

with this program mentioned severe manufacturing complications, power consumption, and scalability [7]. More recently, FlexSys designed and tested a Mission Adaptive Compliant Wing that exercised an adaptive trailing edge. This wing offered a smooth, variable trailing edge designed for high altitude endurance aircraft using stretchable skin. Testing proved to lower drag over a large range of lift with minimal weight and power penalties. This design was optimized to resist deflection under significant external aerodynamic loading [8] (Figure 2). Multiple other studies have been able to demonstrate controlled twist of morphing wings [9,10].

Figure 2: Adaptive variable wing camber technology.

2.1 Compliant Mechanism Systems

Compliant mechanisms (CM) derive their name from the fact that they achieve mobility, at least in part, through compliance, i.e., elastic deformations of one or more of their links and joints, rather than exclusively through relative motion at the joints [11]. The strength-based design of CM usually makes CM light weight, low power, no or minimal assembly and maintenance, no backlash, and produce a longer life span compared to stiffness-based multi-body designs. The conformal shape variation is possible using distributed compliance rather than using lumped compliance that is using local deformation. Distributed compliance may also avoid high stress concentration which reduces the fatigue life significantly. Due to single body construction, it can generally be scaled to meso- or micro-scale mechanisms.

2.2 Tabletop model of Variable Camber Compliant Wing

FlexSys has developed morphing surfaces for fixed wing and rotorcraft applications [12]. Their leading and trailing edge surfaces were driven by separate actuators. AFRL's VCCW research and development focuses on controlling both leading and trailing edges for wing camber variation using single actuation. The wing camber control with single actuation can decrease the number of actuators and empty those spaces for fuel or other payloads. Design and analysis accounts for external loads, the direction of actuation, displacement, space limitation, structural integrity for wind tunnel tests, and many other requirements for the final design. Several design modifications were made to meet design requirements addressed previously and the VCCW tabletop model is shown in Figure 3. The ability of the design to change section camber by 6 % under aerodynamic load and vary the camber along the span (similar to wing twist) was demonstrated using a bench top model.

Figure 3: AFRL Variable Camber Compliant Wing Prototype (1 ft span, 2 ft chord) (a) Undeformed wing geometry (b) Deformed (6% camber change) (c) Twist.

2.3 Potential Benefits – Drag reduction (Camber Change vs Flap deflection)

Consider a NACA 0010 airfoil profile with a plain trailing edge flap and hinge point at $x/c = 0.75$. The flapped airfoil will undergo a change in camber and effective angle of attack as the flap is deflected by an angle δ as shown in Figure 4.

Figure 4: Flap deflection model.

Using the aerodynamic modeling program XFOIL [13] the 2D performance of a flapped airfoil section versus a change in profile camber was investigated for a series of 10% thick NACA four digit series of airfoils with maximum camber location fixed at 40% chord. A large change in camber is required to achieve an equivalent increase in lift compared to a relatively small flap deflection. At zero degree angle of attack, a 6% change in maximum camber is required to match the section lift coefficient for a small 10° flap deflection (Figure 5a). In further comparison of the NACA 6410 with its 6% camber change over the NACA 0010 with 10° flap deflection, the higher cambered airfoil has a lower section drag coefficient, and much higher predicted section L/D at small angles of attack compared to the NACA 0010 airfoil with 10° flap deflection (Figure 5b). At an angle of attack of 6° the NACA 6410 has a section L/D ≈ 150 compared to L/D ≈ 75 for the NACA 0010 airfoil with 10° flap deflection. The actual L/D performance may not be as drastic as shown in 2D XFOIL analysis due to factors that were not considered in this simple analysis such as 3D effects or surface finishing. However, this simple analysis result is enough to provide the reason to pursue this conformal wing technology. Decreases in induced drag could also be realized by actively adjusting wing camber along the span. A variable camber wing offers the ability to maximize fuel reduction by modifying the wing camber throughout a flight adapting to a specific flight/mission condition or desired vehicle configuration with a wing contour that gives the best performance at those conditions, which may not be obtainable by using a conventional flapped wing.

3 VARIABLE CAMBER COMPLIANT WING

3.1 Design and Analysis

Design and analysis of the prototype VCCW followed a natural progression from conceptual design of the compliant mechanism to final design of the wing installation in the VWT. The entire process was guided by a limited number of basic requirements, which opened the design space to non-traditional materials and manufacturing processes. These non-traditional solutions enabled both rapid prototyping and the integration of lightweight compliant materials into the final wing design.

The objective of the wing design was to achieve a 6% change in maximum camber with standard

NACA four digit series profile targets. The NACA profile targets chosen were NACA 2410 thru NACA 8410. These section profile targets each have a 10% maximum thickness and a constant location of maximum camber (at 40% chord), but with a variation in maximum camber from 2 to 8%.

Figure 5: Comparison between camber change and flap (a) C_l comparing NACA 0010 + $\delta 10^\circ$ and NACA6410 (d) L/D comparing NACA 0010 + $\delta 10^\circ$ and NACA6410.

The fundamental design requirement for the compliant mechanism was to start with an initial NACA 2410 profile and use a single actuation force to deform the profile to a NACA 8410. Wing deformation is then produced using a series of compliant mechanisms, which act independently to produce either uniform or non-uniform camber across the span. Note that the specification of NACA profiles is simply to provide well-known targets for the initial and final shapes (and the corresponding aerodynamics). Custom initial and final shapes, as well as intermediate shapes, would be accommodated by essentially the same design and analysis process.

Nonlinear finite element analysis (FEA) models were developed and utilized for a host of trade studies to evaluate shape under aerodynamic load, materials, and structural strength. Results of these studies helped guide the design from the conceptual compliant mechanism to a scaled prototype utilized for bench testing and small-scale wind tunnel testing to the full scale VCCW installed and tested in the VWT. A one foot span section of the wing was built to validate the design, construction methods, and actuation control of the wing. Continuous profile shape change across the span and variable profile change along the span was demonstrated on the benchtop and in a small developmental wind tunnel. The final wing design resulted in a non-typical wing structure consisting of a rigid main spar, flexible ribs, composite skin, and embedded actuators.

The wing profile shape is controlled by miniature electronic actuators. The actuators are distributed in the wing to allow variation of the wing maximum camber along the span (e.g. generating variation of section lift across the span). Actuators are controlled independently using a microcontroller that commands and achieves desired positioning using a position feedback signal.

Parameter	Value
c	2 ft (0.61 m)
b	6 ft (1.83m)
S	12 ft ² (1.115 m ²)
AR	3
U_∞	50 Knots (25.72 m/s)
Re	1.05×10^6
q_∞	0.057 psi (393.53 Pa)

Table 1: Design parameters and nominal objectives.

The VWT entry was planned to demonstrate a lift coefficient change with profile shape change at a

low to moderate angle of attack range (up to $\alpha = 8^\circ$) with a freestream velocity of 25.7 m/s (50 knots). The prototype VCCW is a straight rectangular wing with nominal dimensions of 1.82 m (6 ft) span and 0.61 m (2 ft) chord. The short span results in a low aspect ratio model. The span was chosen to enable wing installation in other wind tunnels, and it also resulted in an appropriate sized model for AFRL's VWT. Table 1 lists the nominal design parameters and tunnel conditions.

3.2 Full Size Model (6ft span)

Prior to wind tunnel testing, spanwise geometry of the wing was obtained using a 3D optical geometry measurement system (Figure 7a). This was necessary to determine the camber along the span according to applied actuation, also to recognize the exact profiles to be tested in the tunnel. The extracted section profiles provided a geometry for aerodynamic analysis in XFLR5. The maximum camber of the middle wing section for several different actuator positions is shown in Figure 7b. The actuator position has been non-dimensionalized by the full actuator stroke (FS), and is given in percent of full stroke (%FS). The change in section camber at the middle rib is nearly linear with actuator position.

Figure 7: (a) VCCW mounted for 3D optical measurement (b) Extracted profile shape parameters of 6 ft model.

3.3 Comparison of the Actual Wing Geometry with target NACA shapes

Aerodynamic predictions of the wing forces and moments have been made with high speed design tool. The section profiles obtained with the optical geometry measurement system were used to develop a wing model in XFLR5 aerodynamic modeling software. XFLR5 uses two dimensional viscous results from XFOIL [13] to incorporate viscous effects to a 3D panel method. The 3D panel method implemented in XFLR5 is explained in more detail in the XFLR5 documentation [14], and [15,16]. Aerodynamic force predictions of an AR 3 wing with a continuous NACA profiles, and the VCCW profiles are shown in Figure 8. The section profiles of the VCCW are relative to the main spar, so local twist in the airfoil shifts the $\alpha_L = 0$ of each configuration. This is noticeable in Figure 8a when comparing the predicted C_L of the VCCW with $x_{act} = 32\%$ FS and a wing of uniform NACA 2410 profiles along the span. The C_L versus angle of attack plot in Figure 8a shows the VCCW actuated between 32% and 59% FS does not achieve the same range in C_L over the angle of attack range as a wing with uniform NACA target profiles could. However, in practice, the range achieved is rather large, and a manufactured morphing wing may not achieve the exact aerodynamic performance as the design. Characterization and/or detailed computational modeling of the manufactured wing geometry would be important to build a relationship between actuator position and aerodynamic performance to be used in aircraft development. Figure 8b shows a higher predicted drag coefficient of the VCCW compared to the goal wing geometry in all profiles except for the $x_{act} = 59\%$ FS configuration. This makes the VCCW peak L/D smaller than the goal wing.

Figure 8: Predictions of an AR = 3 wing with the targeted NACA section profiles compared to the actual VCCW scanned geometry.

Figure 9: Predictions of an AR = 3 wing with the targeted NACA section profiles compared to the actual VCCW scanned geometry.

As an example of the effect of section profile shape on aerodynamic performance, consider the NACA 5410 and VCCW with $x_{act} = 50\%$ FS. The midspan wing profile at $\alpha = 0^\circ$ of NACA 5410 configuration is shown in Figure 9. We can see that even a minor change in profile shape effects the load distribution over the wing and results in a higher predicted drag for the VCCW and lower peak L/D as in figure 8. This simple comparison demonstrates the strong effect of minor changes to section profile shape on aerodynamic performance, and speaks to the complexities of designing morphing wings.

4 EXPERIMENTAL SETUP AND RESULTS

The prototype VCCW was tested in AFRL’s VWT at Wright-Patterson AFB (Figure 10). The VWT has a 3.65m (12 ft) diameter open jet test section and offers continuous flow speeds up to approximately 46 m/s (150 ft/s). Note that the flow is vertically upward (positive x-direction). Custom, identical fixtures at each end are secured to the outside of the test section walls and pipe supports extend from the fixtures inward to support the wing and permit adjustments to angle of attack.

4.1 6 ft Wind Tunnel Model and Vertical Wind Tunnel Test Setup

The wing, which has dimensions of a 6 ft (1.8 m) span by 2 ft (0.61 m) chord, is centrally mounted within the 12 ft (3.7 m) diameter VWT test section. The AFRL VWT facility was chosen for testing the VCCW because of its large size, ability to operate at the desired flow conditions, and good optical access. Several unique diagnostics methods were used to understand the performance of the flexible compliant mechanism wing under aerodynamic load. The test section of the VWT is accessible to test personnel, with plenty of room to mount optical measurement equipment, light sources, and other equipment used in this test to perform surface oil flow visualization and DIC. Installation of the prototype VCCW in the VWT required a new mounting fixture because a model of this nature (size and flexible structure) had not previously been installed and tested in the VWT. In addition to needing a mounting fixture to hold the model in the flowstream, there was no aerodynamic force measurement system available to test an article of this size in the VWT. A test fixture with embedded load cells is under development, but analysis, calibration, and validation of the aerodynamic force measurement system is ongoing and is presented [18]. Pressure taps have also been installed at mid-span and two additional spanwise locations along the suction surface only, in order to show the change in loading along the wing. Local section lift coefficient was calculated by surface static pressure measurements

made near the wing mid-span.

Figure 10: (a) Wing test fixture design shown in VWT test section. (b) Actual wing installed test fixture.

The increase in the difference between the upper and lower surface pressure coefficient over the majority of the chord demonstrates the strong effect of the profile camber change on aerodynamic loading. Integration of the static pressure coefficient yields the section lift coefficient per unit span near wing mid-span which is presented in Figure 11a versus angle of attack relative to the spar. It is important to note that this is not the same section lift coefficient that would be obtained in a two dimensional flow experiment or analysis since the measurements were made on a low aspect ratio finite wing. The mid-span section lift coefficient calculated using a three dimensional panel method is plotted alongside the experimental results in Figure 11a. The actual scanned wing geometry was used in the analysis. The experimental section lift coefficient increases as camber increases and vice versa. $\alpha_{l=0}$ also decreases as actuator position (and camber) increases. These results are consistent with the known effect of airfoil camber change on section lift coefficient. There is a difference in the slope and less agreement between the section lift coefficients at lower angles of attack. This could be caused by several factors that require additional analysis to fully understand.

The experimental and predicted pressure coefficient distribution at $\alpha_{\text{spar}} = 0^\circ$ and 8° are shown in Figure 11b. Examining the $x_{\text{act}} = 32\%$ lowest camber experimental lift coefficient versus predicted it is obvious that there is better agreement at $\alpha_{\text{spar}} = 8^\circ$ compared to lower angles of attack. Notable differences in the experimental and predicted pressure distributions at 8° angle of attack is in the leading edge area of both the pressure and suction surface. The predicted pressure distribution based on digital scans of the wing shows a very sharp suction peak at the leading edge followed by a strong adverse pressure gradient. The experimental pressure distribution indicates downstream shift in the leading edge suction peak, followed by a slightly stronger adverse pressure gradient. It is not surprising that there is a difference in the leading edge pressure profiles in the experimental and predicted cases. The wing is flexible, especially in the leading edge area compared to traditional wings. The unique composite skin, semi-flexible leading edge area, and large spacing between ribs means the skin was expected to deform under aerodynamic load. Any changes in the leading edge area shape could certainly affect the flow over the wing by changing the pressure distribution. The overall shape of the experimental and predicted pressure distribution at the lower angle of attack shown in Figure 11b are very similar, but the lower surface and upper surface downstream of the pressure peak are off in magnitude. Surface oil flow visualization was used at several different angles of attack and camber settings in order to understand the flow over the upper surface of the wing. The results were very interesting and several cases are shown in the following figures.

Figure 11: (a) Measured section lift coefficient at midspan compared to prediction (b) Comparison of experimental and predicted pressure coefficient for $x_{act} = 32\%$ FS (lowest camber tested).

Surface oil flow visualization of the upper wing surface with $x_{act} = 32\%$ FS, $\alpha_{span} = 0^\circ$ is shown in Figure 12a compared with pressure coefficient. The colors of the original image have been inverted in order to improve contrast. A view of the oil pattern across the entire span is shown in the left side of Figure 12a, and a close up of the mid-span region where the pressure taps are located is shown in the upper right image of Figure 12a. The wing tip vortices can be seen in the full span photo as well as the boundary layer transition region. The close up view of the mid-span region shows the complexity of the flow field at the leading edge area and in the transition region. The dashed vertical lines at approximately 20% and 25% chord highlight a shear line across most of the span at near the upper surface pressure peak. Upstream of the dashed line at 20% chord, the flow is boundary layer appears primarily laminar. In between the two vertical lines is a complex region with strong differences in oil pattern along the span. It is certainly a transitional area of three dimensional flow. In some regions between the two vertical dashed lines, such as the area near the markers, the oil pattern does not move indicating either very low shear stress or separation followed by a wiping of the oil consistent with an area of short laminar separation and turbulent reattachment forming a short separation bubble. On the downstream side of the reattachment line is an area where the oil has been wiped away indicating an area of high shear stress consistent with a turbulent boundary layer. The horizontal lines emanating from the points marked a and b mark the edge of regions in which the boundary layer has been tripped to turbulent by an upstream disturbance. In the case of point a the composite surface has a blemish that appears to trip the boundary layer to turbulent creating a strip that expands laterally in both directions downstream of the point a. Transition of the boundary layer to turbulent occurs much further forward in the experiment than would be expected with a NACA 2410 profile (not shown) at zero angle of attack. The plot of pressure coefficient plot also shows a stronger adverse pressure coefficient immediately following the minimum pressure peak at 20% chord, which could cause laminar boundary layer separation.

Figure 12b shows the oil flow visualization at $\alpha_{spar} = 4^\circ$ compared to the pressure coefficient at mid-span. The wing tip vortices are noticeably stronger at the higher angle of attack, and the oil flow pattern shows more variation compared to the lower angle of attack. At this higher angle of attack the minimum pressure coefficient has moved forward to approximately 15% chord and is followed by a much stronger adverse pressure gradient. The oil flow visualization shows large sections along the span where the boundary layer has tripped to turbulent prior to the pressure peak. The close up view near mid-span shows a large spanwise region where the boundary layer appears tripped (area between the dashed lines in the streamwise direction) compared to the areas marked b where there appears to be laminar separation with turbulent reattachment. The separation bubble is about 50% longer in the streamwise direction compared to the lower angle of attack. There is no evidence of a laminar

separation bubble along approximately the first 30% of the right wing tip (top of figure). Along the left half of the wing the spanwise regions without evidence of a laminar separation bubble are much narrower and are at spanwise locations supported by a rib. Figure 12a-Figure 12b show significant spanwise variation in the boundary layer transition region and what appears to be regions of laminar boundary layer separation and reattachment. That being the case, it is not surprising that there is some disagreement between the pressure coefficient distribution predicted by the panel method and experiment.

Figure 12: (a) Surface oil flow visualization of the wing upper surface, $x_{act} = 32\%$ FS, $\alpha_{span} = 0^\circ$, $U_{in} = 25.6$ m/s (57 mph), $Re = 1.05 \times 10^6$. Flow is from the left to the right of the image (b) Surface oil flow visualization of the wing upper surface, $x_{act} = 32\%$ FS, $\alpha_{span} = 4^\circ$, $U_{in} = 25.6$ m/s (57 mph), $Re = 1.05 \times 10^6$. Flow is from the left to the right of the image.

DIC was used to understand the deformation of the wing under aerodynamic load. The top image in Figure 13 shows the out of plane displacement of the upper surface of the wing under aerodynamic load at $x_{act} = 32\%$ FS. Data was acquired over the entire upper surface of the wing except for the edges and corners of planform. The amount of wing leading edge and trailing edge that was unable to be correlated depended on the angle of attack and actuator position. The out of plane displacement has been plotted at three streamwise positions in the plot at the bottom of Figure 13. The out-of-plane displacement pattern shows the highest deformation at the trailing edge and in the middle of the span as would be expected in a wing rigidly supported on each end. The black line corresponds to the approximate location of the main spar. The displacement of the supports at the wing tips is very small (< 1 mm), and even at higher angle of attack and higher camber was only 2mm, demonstrating the rigidity of the wing test fixture. The lower plot in Figure 13 shows a periodic spatial pattern in the out of plane skin displacement near the leading edge and in the area of the main spar with peaks and valleys that correlate with rib locations.

From the plots in Figure 13 we see that the trailing edge was deforming nearly three times as much as the main spar and leading edge area. This is expected to have a similar aerodynamic effect as a small negative trailing edge flap deflection. In order to get a better idea of the deformation of a section profile shape and the effect it may have on aerodynamic forces, the out of plane displacement was analyzed at mid-span in the streamwise direction.

5 SUMMARY

A Variable Camber Compliant Wing was designed, fabricated, and tested in the AFRL VWT. The wing was tested at flow speeds up to 25.7 m/s (50 knots) at a Reynolds number of one million. The profile camber was changed through actuator motion from 32 % to 59% FS with the wind on and over an angle of attack range of -4° to 8° measured relative to the spar. The wing can actively re-contour

the airfoil camber up to 6% and the entire skin is seamless, continuous, and made of a single piece non-stretchable composite skin. Smooth conformal shape of the wing is attained by distributed elastic deformation from the underlying compliant mechanism and 3D shape change is also capable through variation of camber along the spanwise direction using distributed actuation system along the span. Single actuation control for both leading and trailing edge deflection is another very unique aspect of VCCW compared to previous technologies. It was fabricated using advanced manufacturing technology enabling a solution that is a light weight, low power, and low cost. Multiple diagnostic techniques were applied for the wind tunnel testing including 3D optical measurement of the VCCW shape, flow visualization using smoke and oil, pressure and load measurement, and aeroelastic deflection measurements using DIC system. The oil flow visualization indicated that flow over the upper wing surface varied considerably along the span, especially at higher angles of attack. The boundary layer is tripped to turbulent over discrete portions of the span forward of the minimum pressure peak. In some cases the boundary layer is clearly tripped by blemishes in the surface finish which could be easily improved in the future. In regions where the boundary layer flow is not tripped, the boundary layer transition region is evident. At lower maximum section camber there is evidence to suggest short laminar separation bubbles with turbulent reattachment along portions of the span. 3D digital image correlation was used in the wind tunnel to measure the surface deformation with and without the wind on. The displacement of the wing is consistent with a deformable structure supported on both ends (wing tips in our case), with higher deformation in the mid span compared to the wing tips. Deformation of the wing tips near the mounting fixture was low (< 2mm). Analysis of the upper surface displacement near midspan indicated that the trailing edge deformation due to aerodynamic loading, similar to a flap deflection was on the order of tenths of degrees measured relative to a virtual pivot point at the main spar. The highest trailing edge deflection was -0.8° , and occurred at the highest camber setting, and largest angle of attack. Deformation of the upper surface at the leading edge region was also observed, especially at the lower angles of attack at which the stagnation point has moved to the upper surface. The surface displacement measured by digital image correlation was very useful to understand the deformation of the wing compared to prediction. The VCCW technology showed potential capabilities to maximize the aerodynamic efficiency gains by adapting the airfoil shapes throughout a flight and to enable wing reconfiguration to decrease noise. More improvement and testing are scheduled to understand flexible wings and mature the technology.

Figure 13: Out of plane displacement of the upper wing surface with wind on compared to wind off.

The top images show the displacement over the entire surface, and the bottom plot shows the displacement along the span at three chordwise locations. (a) $x_{act} = 32\%$ FS (lowest camber) with $\alpha_{spar} = 0^\circ$ (b) $x_{act} = 59\%$ FS (lowest camber) with $\alpha_{spar} = 0^\circ$.

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